

MENTAL HEALTH IN A CHANGING EUROPE: POLICY BRIEF

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Mental Health in Europe

The burden of mental health issues is recognized as a global concern, affecting people of all ages, genders, and socio-economic backgrounds. As Europe has been shaken with numerous crises of significant magnitude, known as polycrisis or permacrisis, the European Union (EU) has prioritised pandemics, climate change, digitalisation, socio-economic inequities, migration, conflict and socio-demographic transitions as the most critical threats to mental health in our times.

Mental health is influenced by socio-economic and environmental factors and by intersectionality (e.g., interrelated social inequities based on gender, age, ethnicity, disability, and sexual orientation). Therefore, mental health services require attention to structural and social determinants of mental health as well as personalized approaches. The focus in mental health policy, practice and research has largely been on providing clinical treatments to people with circumscribed mental health concerns. However, the magnitude of the mental health burden in Europe requires a focus on innovative and accessible approaches to prevent mental health concerns and promote positive aspects of mental health.

ADVANCE's European-level analyses

In this context, the aim of the ADVANCE project is to produce guidance and methodologies for innovative, scalable mental health promotion and prevention initiatives addressing specific population groups. These specific (pre-selected) population groups include: youth affected by climate change in Germany; young people affected by socio-economic adversity in Lithuania; adults working in digitalized small and medium enterprises in the Netherlands; adults with a migrant background in Denmark, Finland, and Italy; and older adults in Switzerland. The ADVANCE project sought to better understand the threats to mental health for these specific groups as a first step. Therefore, we carried out situational analyses in seven countries (see *Annex*).

This policy brief is a product of those analyses, primarily intended to assist policy and decision makers in understanding how the current challenges of a transforming Europe affect the mental health of groups in vulnerable situations. It also offers recommendations on how to address gaps at the policy level while advocating for greater respect of human rights and addressing structural injustices.

Key Findings

- ▶ Current and emerging threats to mental health in Europe affect populations in vulnerable situations differently, depending on how new threats interact with the pre-existing challenges faced by each group.
- ▶ Mental health promotion and prevention interventions can build on existing evidence-based practices. However, for these interventions to be effective, its design and implementation need to take into account the complex, interacting social inequities on the basis of age, gender, social status, socio-cultural identity, sexual orientation, disability, and exposure to human rights violations.
- ▶ To be responsive to needs, interventions need to be closely tailored to populations with respect to socio-cultural context with an understanding of the structural factors that affect the mental health and access to care of people in vulnerable situations. This includes considering the stigma and discrimination that may be associated with mental health.

Policy guidance and priority actions

The following key aspects should be considered by policymakers:

INVEST IN BRIDGING THE CURRENT KNOWLEDGE GAPS

More knowledge is needed on the effects of the recent polycrisis on the mental health of groups in vulnerable situations in Europe. Although there is a significant evidence base for prevention and promotion interventions, more knowledge is required to understand how existing evidence

can be generalized to the new mental health threats Europe is facing. In addition, existing research rarely covers issues critical to the implementation aspects of interventions, such as sustainability, scalability, and optimal reach (i.e., taking interventions from rigorous trials to routine practice settings).

ADOPT A CO-CREATION APPROACH TO BUILDING EFFECTIVE PROMOTION AND PREVENTION MENTAL HEALTH INTERVENTIONS

There is a multiplicity of factors to consider when designing or scaling up mental health interventions. It requires a multi-sectoral approach that engages a diversity of stakeholders in a spirit of co-creation

in every aspect of interventions, from the design of the recruitment strategy to the implementation and evaluation.

FOCUS ON STRUCTURAL PROCESSES AND THE REDUCTION OF SOCIAL AND HEALTH INEQUITIES

Especially for prevention and promotion interventions with populations in vulnerable situations, intervention efforts should be embedded in broader effort to address structural injustices, which have been exacerbated by the polycrisis faced by Europe. Given the numerous structural and social determinants to mental health, **mental health priorities should be integrated into policies across a range of**

sectors and at every level of policymaking. Given the complex interactions between social and individual factors determining mental health, greater efforts are needed to implement programs across sectors (e.g., combining mental health and social integration efforts; integrating mental health promotion into the workplace; connecting social and mental health programs for older adults).

ENSURE THE SUSTAINABILITY OF THE INTERVENTIONS OVER TIME

The lack of sustainability of interventions identified in desk reviews present a serious challenge. One of the key success factors that emerged is building trust with targeted populations, thus requiring long-term approaches. Sustainability

should be embedded from the conception phase of interventions so that it is not impacted by the end of short-term funding cycles. Moreover, more intervention studies should embed sustainability into their research objectives.

ADDRESS STIGMA AND DISCRIMINATION

Due to the notable stigma attached to mental health, persons experiencing mental health problems often do not seek help or experience barriers when seeking help. To address this problem, it is necessary to invest in mental health literacy and address prejudices and discrimination bias at various levels (general population; delivery of social and health services). Actors working

with groups in vulnerable situations should have access to interventions and tools that reduce stigma whereas awareness raising campaigns should target the general population. Promotion and prevention interventions should be proactively designed to avoid use of stigmatizing language and avoid stigma on the basis of (digital) literacy and access.

ANNEX: SYNTHESIS OF DESK REVIEWS

An attachment to D1.2 Mental Health in a Changing Europe (Policy Brief)

METHODOLOGY

The ADVANCE project partners carried out rapid desk reviews in six European countries (Denmark, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Switzerland, and the Netherlands) to provide an overview of how specific threats such as climate change, digitalization, migration, socio-economic stressors, and aging affect the mental health of pre-selected populations in those countries. The research then aimed to identify sub-groups at higher risk among the pre-selected populations. Collected data included overall demographic profiles, epidemiology of mental health and psychosocial problems, adversities and sources of distress, socio-cultural aspects, and the existence of and access to psychosocial services.

Due to a different scope of research (i.e. scaling up an intervention that has been proven effective), the information gathered from the Finnish Desk Review will be included in ADVANCE's project policy outcomes at a later stage.

COUNTRY-SPECIFIC FINDINGS

Youth affected by climate change, Germany

The focus of the intervention research in Germany is climate change and its impact on young people between 12 and 25 years old. Overall, a number of studies show that climate change is associated with a significant mental health burden in young people in Germany: climate-related distress is linked to higher depressive symptoms, increased anxiety symptoms and lower reported health-related quality of life. Young people themselves indicate negative, stressful emotions in relation to climate change and that their concerns about the environment limit their sense of joy and cause sleep problems. Youth are impacted by both the direct consequences of climate change through extreme weather events (EWE) (e.g., floods) and changes in their living conditions, as well as indirect and social consequences like the prospect that their and coming generations' living conditions will consistently worsen. Their vulnerability moreover stems from a combination of increased awareness about the effects of climate change and limited resources to impact climate policies and cope with global stressors.

The research team was able to identify two important subgroups at higher risk of negative mental health impacts: climate activists and young people having experienced EWE, such as floods. In addition to the distress experienced by the general population, young activists also report feelings of anger and frustration, disbelief and confusion about politics and politicians, and pressure and stress caused by the workload due to their engagement. For those affected by EWE, feelings of anxiety, helplessness, and extreme tension lingered also after the initial shock had subsided. In addition to this, there are specific risk factors, in form of indirect consequences like intra-family conflicts, little social support, the loss of social networks and relocation.

Young adults affected by socio economic adversity, Lithuania

Young people can be particularly vulnerable to mental health problems. Adolescence and emerging adulthood are critical developmental periods characterised by significant biological, psychological, and social changes that can increase vulnerability to stress and mental health problems. During this period, individuals often experience heightened academic pressures, social expectations, identity exploration, and financial instability, all of which can contribute to increased psychological distress. These factors are exacerbated when individuals experience socio-economic adversities, increasing their vulnerability to mental health problems, as well as discrimination and stigma.

The desk review, predominantly based on data from student populations, highlights several vulnerabilities among Lithuanian youth. These include exposure to bullying, adverse childhood experiences, financial hardships, unemployment, residence in rural areas, physical disabilities, being female, as well as identifying as a sexual or gender minority.

Adults in digitalised work settings in Small-to-Medium Enterprises (SMEs), the Netherlands

In the Dutch context, the focus is on the digitalisation of the workplace as the Netherlands has one of the most digitalised workforces in Europe. Initial research has shown that due to the increased use of digital technologies, employees feel they have

to work more and faster and therefore they are more stressed and experience worse physical and mental health problems. These employees also report being less happy, having more difficulties maintaining a healthy work-life balance, and experiencing more symptoms of burnout.

The desk review identified a body of research which reveals that factors such as age, gender, education, and higher levels of responsibility increase the risk for work-related mental health problems and stigmatization in the context of digitalized work settings in the Netherlands. As a result, the following groups are at higher risk of experiencing mental health concerns:

- Women, younger employees (< 35 years), senior managers, and employees with preparatory practical education or less (\leq VMBO) or theoretical education (\geq HBO) are generally more vulnerable to burnout symptoms in the workplace
- Women and younger (< 35 years) and older (> 50 years) employees suffer more from symptoms related to technostress
- Senior managers, women, younger (< 35 years) or new employees (e.g., started in the company within the last 6 months), and employees with preparatory practical education or less (\leq VMBO) or theoretical education (\geq HBO), suffer from difficulties with hybrid working for various reasons
- Men, younger employees (< 35 years), and employees with preparatory practical education or less (\leq VMBO) or theoretical education (\geq HBO), are less likely to disclose their mental health issues at work
- Moreover, men and employees with preparatory practical education or less (\leq VMBO) expect to experience more negative work outcomes when they do disclose mental health concerns (e.g. social consequences of getting fired)

Adults with a migrant background, Italy

Italy is one of the primary destination countries for migrants seeking asylum in Europe. The migrant population, including undocumented migrants, asylum seekers, refugees, internationally displaced persons, labour migrants and other populations on the move faces a multitude of stressors and potentially traumatic events throughout the various stages of their migration journey. Based on a number of studies among migrant populations resettled in Italy, ADVANCE project partners

identified that people with the highest risk for mental health concerns with limited educational attainment and facing socio-economic challenges, particularly those without stable employment. Three main groups emerged as at higher risk in the desk review:

- Refugees from West Africa, whose vulnerability might be related to adversities on the migration route (i.e., central Mediterranean route), particularly through Libya. This route exposes them to conflict-related and interpersonal (gender-based) violence, and a highly protracted and challenging journey. Racism and discrimination are also experienced once resettled in Italy.
- Asylum seekers with pending asylum applications for international protection. Their psychological distress is linked to factors such as the long wait for asylum decisions, and the difficulty of finding long-term employment.
- Migrant women report poorer mental and physical health outcomes than men. This may be linked to ethnic discrimination and interpersonal and gender-based violence. They often work irregularly, facing heavy workloads and emotional stress. These factors may limit access to healthcare services and increase risks of developing mental health problems. Discrimination based on refugee and gender status may also be connected with underemployment. During the perinatal period, migrant women may find it difficult to access healthcare services due to costs, and may perceive a lack of cultural sensitivity, particularly for infant and young child feeding practices.

Adults with a migrant background, Denmark

Migration is the chosen focus in the context of Denmark with particular emphasis on questions related to migration status, social integration, and their effects on mental health. Based on a body of literature in Denmark, the ADVANCE project partner has found (similar to the situation in Italy) that vulnerabilities for migrants in relation to mental health are linked to socio-economic and environmental determinants and traumatic experiences happening both pre- and post- arrival. The desk review identified three main sub-groups:

- Newly arrived refugees face long waiting times for the handling of their asylum application resulting in economic hurdles and social exclusion due to the low benefits they are entitled to and no opportunities to enter the labour market. In addition, they have

poor access to general health and specific mental health services leading to lack of early recognition of and intervention for trauma.

- Former child refugees (i.e., adult refugees who arrived in Denmark as children) may have experienced increased exposure to violence, family separation, absence of proper care, socioeconomic adversity, labour market marginalization and other social inequities, higher levels of mortality and psychiatric care, poor education attainment and labour market outcomes, limited access to healthcare and inconsistent health data transfer when turning 18 hindering continuum of care.
- People with higher levels of exposure to potentially traumatic events, including gender-based violence and torture survivors, represent a group with a need for more comprehensive care. The pre-migration experience to traumatic experiences increases the risk for mental health problems compared to non-exposed groups. Mental health needs in these populations are diverse. Many refugees experience barriers to accessing care.

Older adults, Switzerland

As the tide of global aging rises, the urgency for informed public health interventions and policy development in the domain of gerontology becomes paramount. Therefore, the focus in Switzerland is on the aging population. Numerous international and national studies have shown that mental health and cognitive functioning are pivotal determinants of quality of life in older adults, a group that is steadily increasing. In this context, cognitive functioning — which includes memory, attention, language, and problem-solving abilities — is a crucial aspect of mental health in later life. Knowing that mental health critically interacts with cognitive functioning, especially in subpopulations with lower educational background and compromised socioeconomic resources, underlines the multifaceted challenges for healthcare systems, policymakers, and society at large.

The situation analysis identified three dimensions of vulnerability in this group: cognitive functions, physical abilities and health, and mental health. However, it is crucial to note that older adults are a very heterogeneous group. Health and functioning in old age are not uniformly distributed and - beneath the division between the third and fourth ages - depend on a range of social factors such as education, income, gender and, migratory status.

Additionally, experiences accumulated over the life course, such as engagement in cognitively stimulating activities and social relationships, influence how older adults cope with aging challenges and may also contribute to their vulnerability.

ADDITIONAL REFERENCES

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ADVANCE: Addressing mental health vulnerabilities from adolescence to older age: innovating prevention science for times of change

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